

Effect of Influencer Marketing and Peer Pressure on Compulsive Buying Behavior through Panic Behavior Disorder: Empirical Evidence from Cosmetic Industry of Pakistan

Sundus Riaz¹, Maryam Ansar², Hooria Sajjad³, Alishba Shabbir⁴, Saif Ullah Khan⁵

Abstract

In the contemporary era, prodigious growth has been experienced by beauty products due to the influencer marketing and peer pressure. Various studies showed that cosmetic companies, marketing agencies, and influencer marketing aim to determine significant factors affecting the Buying Behavior and recommendation of consumers in the beauty and cosmetics industry. The objective of current research study is to examine the effect of influencer marketing and peer pressure on compulsive buying behaviour through panic behaviour disorder. Moreover, the study would explore the consumer panic behavior disorder related to cosmetic products. The study has conducted an in-depth contemporary literature review regarding the influence of peer pressure and influencer marketing towards compulsive buying behavior via panic behaviour disorder. Hence, data was collected by gathering primary data from 319 female student respondents from Lahore. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was used as an appropriate methodology because it suitably identifies the causal relationship between factors. Moreover, the validity and reliability of the scales was examined using Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA). The data would be analysed using AMOS and SPSS in order to get results of hypothesis. The study results showed that influencer marketing (stimulus factor) arouse panic behavior disorder (Organism), which lead the customer to response behavior in the form of compulsive buying behavior. One of the important contribution of the study is the primary analysis of effect of influencer marketing and peer pressure on compulsive buying behaviour through panic behaviour disorder which have never been tested by previous researchers. The research study would be helpful to contribute different ideas and knowledge to cosmetic companies, compulsive buyers and marketing researchers. Hence, it would make researchers capable so they could get insight about consumers' buying behaviour and devise different policies respectively.

Keywords: Influencer Marketing, Peer Pressure, Panic Behavior Disorder, Compulsive Buying Behavior, SEM, AMOS, SPSS, Female Students

1. Introduction

Consumer culture has inaugurated new social and market trends including compulsive buying behavior. Impulsive purchasing has been researched in different economies as opposed to agricultural economy like Pakistan (Tarka et al., 2020). The commercialization-promoting patterns are spreading across from the West, particularly, U.S toward Eastern Europe. Buyers from this phenomenon are influenced by advertising efforts of organizations (Tang et al., 2021). Whereas, Development in showcasing of the executive's imaginative pattern increases the worth of the association. Commercials through well-known mediums are the best and quickest advertising method to capture attention of target buyers (Nguyen et al., 2021). Advertisements and promotion media-houses are designing different advertising plans which influence shoppers' motivational behavior for purchasing beauty care products (Abraham et al., 2022). This study identifies whether habitual purchasing is a problem faced by customers and to generate knowledge into customer behavior towards web-based shopping of electronic merchandise within Pakistan economy. The study will identify factors which impact web-based shopping and shopper behavior to purchase products in Pakistan. In Pakistan, web-based promotions have a functioning impact on diminishing impulsive purchasing conduct and impacting online buyers. The other significant element is that most individuals have negative involvement with web-based shopping because of urgent purchasing conduct in this area (Nielsen, 2010). There is an overall concern that beauty care products are bought by females, accepting that these items might work on their appearance and character (Majid, 2015).

¹ Faculty of Management Studies, UCP Business School, University of Central Punjab, Lahore, Pakistan

² Faculty of Management Studies, UCP Business School, University of Central Punjab, Lahore, Pakistan

³ Faculty of Management Studies, UCP Business School, University of Central Punjab, Lahore, Pakistan

⁴ Faculty of Management Studies, UCP Business School, University of Central Punjab, Lahore, Pakistan

⁵ Institute of Management Studies, University of Peshawar, Peshawar, Pakistan

Pakistani females are spending a considerable amount of their finances on purchasing products (Khan et al, 2021). In the recent era, different brands sell similar items, and buyers have many alternative choices, and many variables are influencing their purchasing behavior (Kumar et al., 2014). Hence, irrespective of promotion and advertisement the Covid-19 pandemic has also shift the behavior regarding how individuals make purchases (Meyer et al., 2020, Sheth et al., 2020). The compulsive buying behavior of buyers depends on two variables. The primary portion incorporates buyer conduct towards factors influencing their purchasing behavior and customer conduct and emotional buyer cycle (Omar et al., 2021). Utilization and purchaser conduct dependent on overall setting (Sivamaruthi et al., 2018). Media house showcase promotes organizations who are building their image and conviction because of consumers trust in their organizations (Nadanyiova et al, 2020). Individual consideration and revitalizing industry are among Asia's quickest-developing buyer-based ventures. Relational impacts, e.g. Peer pressure contributes a significant impact on the behavior of the buyers. The main component that influences buyers is the purchaser's social climate. Peer pressure implies being impacted by companions to accomplish something special. Studies have shown that friends are considered as a significant factor which influences young people while choosing items (Vinayak & Arora, 2018).

The review focuses on addressing the theoretical gaps in the literature regarding advertising patterns in Pakistan. To guide organizations and future manager's promotion done by influencer marketing, also, this study will identify critical variables which influence shoppers' desecration (needs and wants) in the health and beauty care products industry (Abraham, 2022). Researchers can identify factors connected impulse purchasing found in numerous nations during the COVID-19 outbreak (Xiang, 2021). During the COVID-19 pandemic, the utilization of web advertisement improves trade worldwide; hence, clients are more mindful and avoid pitfalls to make ideal choices. This study investigates the client's motivation towards purchasing during the COVID-19 pandemic (Naeem, 2020). Details study on COVID-19 and buyer purchasing behavior was not accessible for reviews (Patil, 2020). The relationship between promotion and peer pressure on compulsive buying behavior mediated through panic is has not been studied in Pakistan (Abraham et al, 2022)

With the increase in urbanization, new shopping buildings are expanding consistently (Zang et al, 2022). Buyer purchasing behavior incorporates both mental and proactive tasks for a purchaser. Customers utilize several factors before buying a product hence the process is quite complex and dynamic (Modi&Jhulka 2012). Since for a long period of time, organizations have attempted to achieve simplification of process in order to make shopping a delightful experience or to simplify the process of shopping such that process becomes easier and according to customer expectation. The need for simplification is for the reason that customers would consider buying the product is according to their needs and wants, eliminating the thought that impulse buying overcome the cognitive process of the customer when purchasing. Nevertheless, customer in control can comprehend their emotional state which might be either positive or negative in nature and make a rational decision making when purchasing a product (Parsad et al, 2021). Compulsion to buy a product randomly or when emotions are involved in it is a major consideration during shopping which needs to be controlled (Tarka & Harnish 2022). The research objectives include: To analyze influencer marketing and peer pressure from compulsive buying behavior and to examine the role of panic behavior disorder between the relationship of influencer marketing, peer pressure and compulsive buying behavior. Moreover, research questions include:

- Does influencer marketing impact Panic behavior disorder?
- Does influencer marketing impact compulsive buying behavior?
- Does panic behavior disorder mediate relationship influencer marketing and compulsive buying behavior?
- Does panic behavior disorder mediate the relationship between peer pressure and compulsive buying behavior?
- Does peer pressure affect compulsive buying behavior?

In this study, quantitative approach is used in order to get insight about results of generated hypothesis. After collection of data, Structural Equation Modeling (S.E.M.) is used to identify causal relationship between factors. A.M.O.S. was used to investigate the relationship between the under-laying constructs.

Under this methodology, first the scales were translated from English to Urdu. In the second phase, data was collected from the respondents. In the third phase, the validity and reliability of the scales was examined through Confirmatory Factor Analysis (C.F.A.). And the fourth and final phase, A.M.O.S. was used to test the relationship between the constructs. The structure of the paper comprises of the supporting theories, an in-depth analysis of literature review, methodology, analysis, results and conclusion.

2. Literature review and Supporting Theories

The research study initiated with literature review and supporting theories because it would develop the understanding and knowledge regarding the subject. Hence, it would develop and explain how present research study would be perfect in current body of knowledge. Further, the study would illustrate the resources reconnoitered by the authors. In order to conduct literature, we had explored following research databases which includes Taylor & Francis, Emerald, Frontiers, Elsevier, MDPI, Springer link, Hindawi, IEEE, PLOS, Wiley etc. Authors has collect research data by gathering 150 research papers out of which about 65-70 research articles were used for our current research study.

2.1. Research Model and Hypothesis Development

2.1.1. Influencer Marketing and Compulsive Buying Behavior

Influencer marketing is a type of marketing influencers obtain a payment which includes free products or financial payment and advertisers have control on the content displayed for the audience (De Veirman et al., 2019). Studies showed that following approach of marketing targets a \$10 billion industry in 2020 and is working to expand its impact on organizations, particularly those working in a business-to-shopper climate. Hardly any organizations in the design, excellence, travel, food, or refreshment ventures are promoting efforts nowadays that do exclude, essentially to some point, cooperation with well-known clients on platforms like Instagram and TikTok. Pairing web-based promotions and social influences can draw many followers through these social platforms (Haenlein et al, 2020).

Compulsive buying behavior is characterized as an impulsive buying behavior, where the client cannot altogether control (Faber and O'Guinn, 1989). Mediahouse promotion is the combination of old and new showcasing techniques where they employ popular and notable individuals in the public arena and via web-based entertainment to give paid advertising content. Media house promotion is characterized as showcasing participation between a party offering support or an item and between a notable and compelling individual - in a climate associated with the Internet - to advertise an item or advertise for a change in the consumer's lifestyle. The impact of a influencer marketing is considerable higher on the consumers buying behavior when they are correctly advertised. Scientists likewise underscored that, as a rule, the buying choices made by purchasers are incautious, alluding to the way that the "media house" utilizes them and hence the presence of the impact increased thus making the compulsive buy to be a well thought and educated buy (Hashem, 2021).

The image of the influencers is portrayed in such a way that the product is glorified, and social importance is promoted with it. According to the point of view of different researchers, the importance of media house cannot be avoided (Jin et al., 2019). Furthermore, web influencers use their influence to promote a good name towards the brand they are pairing up with. This implies that consumers are bound to acknowledge or trust influencer marketings' perspectives when those influencer marketings' team up with brands that relate well to their subject matters (Hair, 2010). Studies analysed that influencer marketing promoting yielded multiple times the profit from venture (R.O.I.) of customary publicizing (Lou, 2019).

Specifically, the present study of examination of online entertainment impact to be reckoned with promotion has been propelled by the following reasons. To start with, nevertheless earlier work outlines a different scope of influencer marketing factors (e.g., validity, accurateness and specialization) and different tools (e.g., endorser-brand fit, copycat and social connection) that affect customer buying behavior (e.g., commitment, brand trust and buying objective), there is no methodical evaluation or integrative examination of the quickly expanding research that spotlights on the peculiarity of S.M.I.s. Along these lines, we need vital and scholastic knowledge of how advertisers can benefit from this new tool (Campbell, 2020).

Second, objectives come from different research fields, and the collection of S.M.I. writing is quickly growing. This has brought about a fairly different cluster of information that needs collection of events. The promoting field, like this, would profit from an integrative structure that blends accessible proof from existing research from different disciplines while tending to the impacts of different influencer marketing factors on attitudinal and social buyer reactions. Third, I.M. is a moving subject among researchers since it is progressively recognized as a significant worldview via online entertainment (Gretzel, 2018). Moreover, (Shamim & Islam, 2022) in their research study argued that influencer marketing plays a significant role in developing the trust among audience which in turn enhance the impulse among viewers and audience towards compulsive buying. Hence, on the basis of following study, we hypothesized that:

H1: Influencer marketing has a positive effect on Compulsive Buying Behavior.

2.2. Peer Pressure and Compulsive Buying Behavior

Peer pressure refer to active efforts from peers in order to influence other individuals to undertake any action. It also consists of passive effects.e.g. not undertaking an action for fear of peer social approvals or in order to achieve peer social approval (Bursztyn et al., 2014). Peer pressure assists with exciting the materialistic qualities and compulsive buying behavior among youthful grown-ups. Pakistani youth have areas of strength for material belonging. In Pakistan, as in different nations, there are areas of strength among assets and kinships since those youthful grown-ups connect fundamentally with peers (Islam et al, 2017). The way every individual arrange with external tensions, at last, decides their utilization decisions and demeanor toward extravagance (Gil et al., 2017).

Understanding peer impact among young people is significant for creating and understanding how to work on different financial arrangements. Peer among youth assumes an essential part during teenage hood. When young people foster profound kinship among their companions and become long-lasting relationship (Guzman et al., 2017). Peer tension towards buying behavior is supposed to be a social phenomenon where individuals from a specific culture may not be impacted adversely; however, the larger part is impacted by the behavior of individuals who oppose what others do (Gulati et al., 2017). Focusing on the different variables that impact youth at their academic achievements is usually hindered by formative difficulties (Chen et al., 2008). A distinct need for encouragement towards conveying freely and achieving targets or objectives. Therefore, by associating with peers the primary advantage is getting accepted within the social circle. Likewise, peer pressure put immense pressure on young people as the social acceptance is a critical factor for entry to the social circle (Moldes et al., 2019).

Peer pressure is the impact of a gathering on individuals' behavior from that gathering to such an extent that the people generally follow what everyone does. In business, understanding the peer pressure is an advantage of central significance. Consequently, understanding peer pressure can be a valuable device to convince customers to follow their friends and purchase the designated items. How this can assist corporate managers with advancing deals and increasing brand awareness is of significant interest to researchers which ultimately impacts the compulsive buying behavior as well (Chang, 2018). Youths are presented with various sorts of social issues from well-being, harmful behavior and to how to act in a friendly climate. Peer pressure significantly affects the mind of young people. Present review centers around the connection between family environment and friend tension among teenagers (Singh, 2017). In this study, we move ideas from sociologies and look at the impact of peer effect on culture. We consider "peer pressure" to be the consolidated impact from each of a singular's neighbors applying impact simultaneously and through impact moving from deviant sources (Morris, 2019). Hence, on the basis of above discussion we hypothesized that:

H2: Peer Pressure has a significant effect on Compulsive Buying Behavior.

2.3. Influencer Marketing and Panic Behavior Disorder

There is very scarce research study that examine the effect of media houses on web-based promotion and effect of buyer reactions of panic behavior disorder while purchasing during the Covid-19. The spread of Covid-19 globally impact the panic behavior disorder caused due to online media in the form of hash tags such as "#toilet-paper-door" and "#toilet-paper-emergency" (Naeem et al., 2021). Hence, Panic Behavior disorder is essentially impacted by a people's impression of the danger forced by the emergency and the feeling of dread toward item shortage. Panic purchasing is a way of dealing with hardship or stress to check

uneasiness and increment food security. While certain reports are stating that the hoarding of products should not be consider as immoral act, because of the necessity to protect and care as the emotion which drive panic behavior disorder (Singh et al, 2021).

Customers are attempting to stay away from stressful situation as they feel it is beyond their control, and they do it by panic purchasing since they see much more trouble from here on out. Aside from whole food, wheat, rice, and beans, purchasers purchase the food they appreciate or have been getting a charge out of (Kaur, 2020). The pandemic situation has caused devastation all over the planet since it began effecting people in December 2019. It effected well-being and created a financial emergency for the world yet additionally caused strange individual ways of behaving, for example, panic purchasing from one side of the planet to the other. In the beginning, the logic behind these unusual ways of behaving is difficult to make sense of (Kuruppu et al., 2020).

Panic behavior (P.B.) is considered as a fascinating behavior particularly seen among people even they were in danger of causing harm to themselves. The expression "panic behavior" comprises two words "insanity" and "purchasing" which has a connection to the term stockpiling (Arafat et al., 2020). It is an irregular way of behaving that has been accounted for unpredictably and panic; nonetheless, P.B. has been accounted for since well before and showed up, particularly during a significant crisis. It has been seen and announced in online media during this COVID-19 pandemic in a few nations. It has been called "the abnormality of an unexpected consumption in purchasing at least one product compared to the overabundance of need incited by an emergency". A gathering of scientist hypothetically portrayed it as an indication of basic struggle and vulnerability during the pandemic, an approach to adapting to an unpleasant condition, acquiring control, and overall difficulty adjusting to the same ways of behaving (Arafat, et al,2020).

Fear is a strong driver of the human way of behaving, significantly additional during seasons of emergency. Panic behavior happens when frenzy and disorder impact the behavior driving individuals to purchase more things than needed. Up to this point, no scale on this has been found in the significant data sets. Subsequently, this exploratory review aims to foster a Panic Buying Scale (PBS) during the COVID-19 pandemic (Lins et al, 2020). Hence, we hypothesized that:

H3: Influencer Marketing has a positive effect on Panic Behavior Disorder.

2.4. Peer Pressure and Panic Behavior Disorder

Peer pressure is the impact of close companions, colleagues, and older members on each other. It is demonstrated by the impact of one individual on others, from group of friends imitating the standards of their respective groups (Bursztyn et al., 2014). Studies show that peer pressure is related to the impact of a group member of comparable age or social level and their effect on each other. Peer pressure has been considered as an unsafe way of behaving normally among young people, for example, deviance, illicit drug abuse, and sexual exploitation. Furthermore, peer pressure might be beneficial ways of behaving and adopting trends when young people are impacted to behavior which seems to be acceptable socially and morally, like cultivating a culture of diligence and thought for other people (Adeoye, 2021).

Shoppers imitating others' activities implies peer pressure as they feel satisfaction by behaviors. Supply chain is helpless against unpredicted purchasing behavior, for example, panic buying and hoarding (Wang, 2020). Peer pressure impacts the indication of introverted behavior among students. A friend can be portrayed as an individual old enough or one routinely connects with others and who will probably impact one's way of behaving. Purchasing behavior is dynamic and generally affected by four fundamental variables - social, cultural, individual, and mental. A customer's buying choice is frequently made relevantly, influenced by a person's current situations and peer pressure (Yuen et al, 2022). Hence, on the basis of above discussion we hypothesized that:

H4: Peer Pressure has a significant positive effect on Panic Behavior Disorder.

2.5. Panic Behavior Disorder and Compulsive Buying Behavior

Panic behavior is define as an impulsive way of behaving by which customers buy things in huge amounts to deflect ingenuity or for see shortages in the future (Herjanto et al, 2021). Research studies have found that cognitive factors, for example, detest, wretchedness, and nervousness, in an individual influence the panic behavior levels in an individual and are essential to get bits of knowledge in Asian nations setting

according to promotion viewpoint (Suresh et al., 2019). Fear is considered as a strong driver of how human behave, considerably during period of an emergency. Panic behavior happens when fear and frenzy impact behavior which drives individuals to purchase more things than usual (Lins, 2020). Yeong et al., (2015) considered impulsive purchasing as a way of life, expressing that this behavior viewpoint incorporates high degrees of stress and tension, which prompts an individual to purchase merchandise.

Steiger & Muller (2015) who expressed this as "the silly and wild securing of things. The primary spotlight is on the demonstration of purchasing, and the bought items a while later scarcely utilized or not even by any means. A social examination could prompt urgent purchasing inclination (Kukar-Kinney et al, 2016). Habitual purchasing is not simply a more grounded variant of imprudent purchasing (Pradhan et al, 2018). It is upheld by low confidence, fixation, depression and uneasiness. It is likewise utilized as an instrument of negative adapting (Zheng et al, 2020). Research have depicted urgent purchasing conduct as a psychological state in which a confined person who lacks the motivation to control and has low confidence joined with tension and realism looks for energy (hammer, 2017).

Habitual buying has been characterized as an overpowering desire to purchase, an addiction towards shopping, which in outrageous conditions can prompt the deficiency of composure and withdrawal disorders, going from disquiet to psychosomatic incapacitation. Compulsive Buying Behavior. is an extreme type of imprudent purchasing. In contrast, scholars believe that it is a constant failure in self-regulation and, like this, considerably more serious than habitual buying (Maccarrone, 2017). Individuals buying behavior and cognitive processes are based impulsivity and compulsivity. Even though compulsivity in the two genders was essentially impacted by the upgrade and adapting thought processes, ladies were affected more by the upgrade rationale, while men were impacted more by the intention to adapt (Jung, 2017).

Analyzing impulsive buying through the system of buyer attitudes might offer basic insight to the knowledge seeing such shopper behavior (Japutra et al, 2020). The most common way of shopping gives a few advantages to enthusiastic purchasers in the short run, which relate to the above-examined shopping inspirations. Hence, on the basis of this we hypothesized that:

H5: Panic Behavior Disorder has a positive effect on Compulsive Buying Behavior.

3. Theoretical Framework

3.1. Stimulus Organism Response (S-O-R) Theory

Stimulus Organism Response (S-O-R) Theory was proposed by Woodworth (1929) as an extension to classic theory of the stimulus–response model. Following model is comprised of three constructs i.e. stimulus, organism, and response (Pandita et al., 2021). It decides the behavioral outcome of any event. The theory expresses that an ecological upgrade may affect the way of behaving or inner sensations of a life form. The inside sensations of a life form can be oblivious, or the individual may know about them deliberately. Acoby (2002) likewise introduced the relationship between buyers and close-to-home reactions regarding their goal, buy, exchange, and return. As per this hypothesis, this study analyzes the force to be reckoned with advertising influence on habitual purchasing conduct. Influencer marketing is an ecological improvement that can influence the customer's purchasing choice. Hence, the following theory would prove beneficial for development of hypothesis for current research study.

3.2. Social Comparison Theory

Social comparison theory was proposed by Festinger in 1954. The theory states that individuals compare themselves relative to others in order to conduct precise self-evaluations. It occur automatically which requires that individuals involve in social comparisons equitably extemporaneously and that requires little effort (Fasbender & Gerpott, 2022). The social comparison theory addresses that a peculiarity in which an individual contrast themselves, as well as other people, for either fulfilling their frailties or their edifices or it is only a type of mental system (Li et al., 2021). It helps lift their mindset, and here and there, individuals additionally entertain themselves with shopping or acting in manners that could be useful to them to work on themselves, assuming they are now disappointed with their ongoing approach to everyday life (Corcoran et al., 2011). Hence, these two theories would support our studies and used for development of research hypothesis.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

4. Methodology

Positivism research approach is considered as a suitable research philosophy for this study. It is characterized as the way of thinking in which genuine and numeric information is utilized for this analysis. Positivists accept that the truth is constant and can be identified from an objective perspective. As per Levin (1988), Positivists imagine that reality can be observed and witnessed impartially. This study employs a deductive approach because it involves testing hypotheses for testing existing theories (Woiceshyn, 2018). Due to the limited time constraint, a cross-sectional study was conducted because it allows the researcher to test one independent variable as the main emphasis of research along with other dependent variables at a specific time (Khan & Khan, 2016). The nature of the research is explanatory and quantitative. Quantitative approach was useful for this study because primary data was collected and this approach is beneficial for statistical, mathematical, or numerical analysis of data acquired through polls, censuses, and surveys (Pantano, 2019). Moreover, this study investigated the studies' causes and effects in certain scenarios study (Given, 2008). This type of research is selected to answer the unique problems relating questions and focus on the deep beneficiary analysis (Thomas, 2008). The population of the research is female students whereas, specifically, data was collected from the female respondents of Lahore belong to different professions, students and homemakers because Lahore is a big and populated city in Pakistan. Professional women and students are consumers. In our research study, we used a sample-to-item ratio theory with the criteria of ten responses against each item to select a sample size of 490 (i.e. 49×10) (Islam et al., 2022). Hence, 490 responses were acquired from different females. Data was collected via a questionnaire survey from 350 respondents (Haier et al, 2010). So, in this study, data collection was made possible through a questionnaire adopted by extant researchers. The study opted for surveys because it has helped authenticate and validate the research results for compulsive buying behavior in youngsters (Bernard & Bernard, 2012). Data was collected from female students of two private sector Universities in Lahore i.e., University of Lahore (UOL) and University of Central Punjab (UCP). A total of 490 questionnaires were distributed and 380 were returned. Out of which 61 questionnaires were incomplete and inappropriate. Hence, 319 respondents were included in the analysis. The response rate was 65.1%.

In this study, a survey was conducted by adopting established measures. The adaptation of another questionnaire is time-consuming, resource intensive, and is expected to be thoroughly tested to confirm validity and reliability. The questionnaire used a five-point Likert Scale ranging from Strongly Agree to Strongly Disagree and closed-questions. The items for influencer marketing were adopted from (Biaudet, 2017) 15-item influencer marketing scale. Peer pressure was measured by using (Brown, 1986). Peer pressure inventory 24 items scale. Panic buying disorder was measured using 4 items scale by Byun and Sternquist (2008) Scale. Lastly, Richmond compulsive buying scale which is a 6 item questionnaire was adopted for measurement of compulsive buying behavior. The data was collected using Google Survey and some questionnaires were filled physically from female students from UOL and UCP students. Hence, total of 319 questionnaires were collected and used for further analysis.

5. Data Analysis and Results

Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) is an appropriate methodology to identify causal relationship between factors. AMOS was used to investigate the relationship between the under-lying constructs. Under this methodology, first the scales were translated from English to Urdu. In the second phase, data was collected from the respondents.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
I.M. 1	349	1	5	3.64	1.112
IM 2	349	1	5	3.46	1.143
IM 3	349	1	5	3.44	1.208
IM 4	349	1	5	3.84	1.163
IM 5	349	1	5	3.80	1.125
IM 6	349	1	5	4.46	.862
PP 1	349	1	5	3.19	1.301
PP 2	349	1	5	3.01	1.205
PP 3	349	1	5	3.10	1.291
PP 4	349	1	5	3.14	1.321
PP 5	349	1	5	3.07	1.313
PP 6	349	1	5	3.12	1.280
PP 7	349	1	5	2.36	1.300
PP 8	349	1	5	3.16	1.326
PB 1	349	1	5	3.66	1.143
PB 2	349	1	5	3.23	1.254
PB 3	349	1	5	3.13	1.235
PB 4	349	1	5	3.35	1.228
PB 5	349	1	5	2.43	1.414
PB 6	349	1	5	2.41	1.400
PB 7	349	1	5	2.65	1.368
CB 1	349	1	5	3.11	1.371
CB 2	349	1	5	2.94	1.298
CB 3	349	1	5	3.38	1.232
CB 4	349	1	5	3.20	1.273
CB 5	349	1	5	3.15	1.276
CB 6	349	1	5	3.36	1.320
CB 7	349	1	5	3.30	1.281
CB 8	349	1	5	2.92	1.403
CB 9	349	1	5	3.15	1.412
CB 10	349	1	5	2.81	1.299
CB 11	349	1	5	2.73	1.376
CB 12	349	1	5	2.67	1.231
CB 13	349	1	5	2.50	1.351
CB 14	349	1	5	2.74	1.305
Valid N (listwise)	349				

In the third phase, the validity and reliability of the scales was examined through Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA). And the fourth and final phase, AMOS was used to test the relationship between the constructs. This strategy combines solid basic inquiry and multi-layer evaluation, analyzing the underlying relationship between estimated factors and constructs (Tarka, 2018). This research uses SEM and IBM

Amos 24 in order to examine the measurement model. There are many advantages to using this methodology. Primarily, it investigates the statistical models to demonstrate the causal relationships among variables. Furthermore, it proficiently measures many constructs and measure small sample sizes and interrelated items by determining measurement and structural model's independent regression analysis (Hair et al., 2020).

Panic buying disorder has become a critical area of interest after the outbreak of Covid-19. It is often considered as a response to environmental stressors. Hence, due to lack of resources as the consequence of pandemic the shifting of consumers and buyers towards compulsive online buying under the pressure of influencer marketing and peer pressure has become an integral area of interest. Due to lack of literature and knowledge that give understanding regarding the psychological consideration of such phenomenon. The objective of current study is to determine the effect of influencer marketing and peer pressure towards compulsive buying behavior through panic behavior disorder in female respondents of Pakistan. The study would contribute by providing understanding of panic buying disorder, authors would expect to contribute to the rehabilitation of consumers and buyers who are facing related behaviors and their associated negative effects on their health. Hence, dissemination of information in the informational index for different factors is ordinariness. To acquire instruments with probability, information should be regularly considered. To test normality, shape, skewness and kurtosis were obtained. To track down deviation, if any, skewness, and kurtosis were estimated through normal distribution. Worth of skewness, kurtoses and histogram with typical distribution are given toward the end. Followed by factors screening, case-level screening was performed. Adequate reaches were utilized to figure out every one of the qualities. The worth of Kurtosis ought to be $<+10$, SKEWNESS $<+3$, as Kline (2005) recommended.

Dependent and independent variables should be aligned in such a way that change in one may cause change in the other. In S.E.M the underlying conflict among the factors of a construct can be problematic. Linearity was tested by using ANOVA in SPSS. No Deviation was found as every factor was connected linearly.

In the above Table, test measurements of factors force to be reckoned with promoting, peer pressure, alarm conduct turmoil and impulsive purchasing conduct, the reaction was gathered utilizing 5-point liker scale (1= emphatically differ to 5= firmly concur. The mean qualities over 3 show the inspiration of the respondents regarding the review Survey. The standard deviation is .6 to .70, which is great. The kurtosis is a win - 3 to +3. In this examination, the kurtosis esteem is between - .389 to .1.93. This additionally shows the danger of the information.

5.1. Reliability Analyses

For the purpose of this study, the measures taken were tested for reliability through Exploratory Factor Analysis. The outcomes were assessed considering Cronbach's Alpha, and measure have a value greater than 0.70 were included in the study. Table 2 shows the results. Cronbach's Alpha values for every one of the factors are above 0.7 ($>.7$). Because of satisfactory levels are reached, nothing was removed out from the instruments.

Table 2: Reliability

Variable	No. of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Influencer Marketing	6	.789
Peer Pressure	8	.748
Panic Behavior Disorder	7	.808
Compulsive Buying Behavior	14	.923

5.2. Correlation

Table 3 shows the correlation among the study variables. The Table depicts that the value of the correlation of each variable with any other variable is greater, which shows that the discriminant validity of every variable is well established. The dependent variable, Compulsive Buying Behavior is positively correlated with all the variables, namely, Panic Behavior Disorder ($r = 0.933$, p -value = 0.01), Peer Pressure ($r = 0.684$,

p-value = 0.01) and Influencer Marketing (r = 0.465, p-value = 0.001). The mediator, Panic Behavior Disorder, is positively and significantly correlated with both the independent variables i.e. Influencer Marketing (r = 0.508, p-value = 0.001) and Peer Pressure (r = 0.752, p-value = 0.001). While both the independent variables, i.e. Influencer Marketing and Peer Pressure, are also significantly and positively correlated (r = 0.681, p-value = 0.001).

Table 3: Correlations

	Panic Behavior Disorder	Peer Pressure	Influencer Marketing	Compulsive Buying Behavior
Panic Behavior Disorder	1			
Peer Pressure	.752**	1		
Influencer Marketing	.508**	.681**	1	
Compulsive Buying Behavior	.933**	.684**	.465**	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

5.3. Measurement Model

After leading the test for the estimation model and its wellness, the underlying Model was tried according to earlier research conversations in writing Survey. The Table demonstrates the consequences of model wellness, showing that the Model fits well. At the same time, the Model shows the way coefficients between factors. The primary Model shows the outcomes for speculation of the examination.

Figure 3: AMOS Structural Model

The outcomes present that the worth of DF/CMIN is 1.866, which is lesser than 3, mirroring the Model fit goodness. The worth of G.F.I. is .872, greater than .800 of edge, which shows the model fit goodness. A.G.F.I. esteem is .824. It has additionally expanded from limit esteem .800 present the model wellness. CFI esteem is .852, which is more noteworthy than .85 showed model wellness. R.M.S.E.A. esteem is .070, which is great for model fit. These outcomes present the best fit primary Model for the study.

Table 4: Model Fitness of Structural Model

	CMIN/DF	CFI	GFI	AGFI	RMSEA
Model	1.866	.852	.872	.824	.070
Threshold Measures	<3 good and <5 sometimes acceptable	CFI >.85 sometimes acceptable >.95 greater >.90 traditional	G.F.I.>.80	AGFI >.80	R.M.S.E.A. <.05 is good, .10 to .05 is moderate and >.10 is bad
	Acceptable	Acceptable	Acceptable	Acceptable	Acceptable

5.4. Regression Weight Analysis

The following Table shows the regression weights.

Table 5: Analyses of Direct Effects

	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Hypotheses
(H1) Compulsive Buying Behavior ← Influencer Marketing	.312			***	Accepted
(H2) Compulsive Buying Behavior ← Peer Pressure	.60	.044	33.368	***	Accepted
(H3) Panic Behavior Disorder ← Influencer Marketing	.381	.035	10.992	***	Accepted
(H4) Panic Behavior Disorder ← Peer Pressure	.862	.041	21.275	***	Accepted
(H5) Compulsive Buying Behavior ← Panic Behavior Disorder	1.236	.029	41.912	***	Accepted

H1 depicts a significant relationship between influencer marketing and compulsive buying behavior. The p-value which is less than 0.05, so there exists a relationship between the dependent and independent variables. The C.R value is 55.22, and the S.E value is .022. Therefore, researcher accepted the null hypothesis.H2 depicts a significant relationship between peer pressure and compulsive buying behavior. The numerical representation of this is also evident that here is a p-value which is less than 0.05, so there exists a relationship between the dependent and independent variables. The C.R value is 33.36, and the S.E value is 0.44. Therefore, researcher accepted the null hypothesis. H3 depicts a significant relationship between influencer marketing and panic behavior disorder. The numerical representation of this is also

evident that here is a p-value which is less than 0.05, so there exists a relationship between the dependent and independent variables. The C.R value is 10.992, and the S.E value is 0.35. Therefore, the researcher accepted the null hypothesis. H4 depicts a significant relationship between peer pressure and panic behavior disorder. The numerical representation of this is also evident that here is a p-value which is less than 0.05, so there exists a relationship between the dependent and independent variables. The C.R value is 21.27, and the S.E value is 0.041. Therefore, the researcher accepted the null hypothesis. H5 depicts a significant relationship between panic behavior disorder and compulsive buying behavior. The numerical representation of this is also evident that here is a p-value which is less than 0.05, so there exists a relationship between the dependent and independent variables. The C.R value is 41.91, and the S.E value is .029. Therefore, researcher accepted the null hypothesis.

5.5. Mediating Model Hypotheses Testing

This Table depicts the mediation relationship between the two selected variables.

Table 6: Analyses of Indirect Effects

Variable	Direct effect with Mediator	Indirect effect	Result
Compulsive Buying Behavior ← Panic Buying Behavior ← Influencer Marketing	.752**	.477***	Partial Mediation
Compulsive Buying Behavior ← Panic Buying Behavior ← Peer Pressure	.455***	.724***	Partial Mediation

5.6. Mediating Model Hypotheses Testing

The analysis is presented in Table 6. Depicts that partial mediation exists through Influencer Marketing with mediator panic behavior disorder on compulsive buying behavior because the direct effect without Mediator is significant, the direct effect with Mediator is significant, the significant value is less than 0.05, and on the other side indirect effect is strongly significant with the less than 0.05 p-value. The analysis is presented in Table 3. depicts that partial mediation exists through peer pressure with mediator panic behavior disorder on compulsive buying behavior because the direct effect without Mediator is significant, the direct effect with Mediator is significant, the significant value is greater than 0.05, and on the other side indirect effect is strongly significant with the less than 0.05 p-value.

6. Discussion

The present research assesses the compulsive buying behavior of young adults in Pakistan. The findings can provide valuable inputs for further understanding the Pakistani market and Pakistani consumers. Its study link to the cosmetic industry. The main objective of this research is to explore the industry. Every industry is based on consumer behavior. So, this research is going to analyze the relationship of compulsive buying behavior with different factors, including influencer marketing, panic behavior disorder and peer pressure. H1 exists between influencer marketing and compulsive buying behavior, and this hypothesis is accepted because its p-value is significant. Generally, influencer marketing strategies never seems constrained or unrelated with the qualities or style of the influencer marketing and in a perfect world, the influencer marketing needs to take an item into its current, individual story (Kacen & Lee, 2002). In this regard, supported design items must be advanced to match or copy the substance of the force to be reckoned with generally posts. The most remarkable consistency between possible clients and the supported item should summon positive buyer judgements and social goals towards the item. The scrutiny could recognize an ideal arrangement for influencer marketing showcasing efforts, whether they unite specific highlights upheld by Instagram (e.g., stickers) or other interpersonal interaction areas (Belanche, 2021). Second hypothesis consists of two variables, peer pressure and compulsive buying behavior. This hypothesis is

accepted due to its significant value. The outcomes demonstrated that friend bunch pressure contributes with exciting the materialistic qualities and impulsive purchasing conduct among youthful grown-ups. Pakistani youth have areas of strength for material belongings. In Pakistan, as in different nations, there are areas of strength among assets and companionships since those youthful grown-ups who connect essentially with peers are more materialistic than those who do not. This outcome affirms that youthful grown-ups who are engaged with peer bunches experience, strain to consent to their companions' ideas while shopping. In the learning and workspaces, youthful people get an impact from their companions, influencing their materialistic perspectives. As per the social trade hypothesis, youthful grown-ups are leaned to assess their material belongings with their companions (Thürmer, 2020). The outcomes in the Pakistani settings are positive in this perspective and per past examinations (Islam et al, 2017). The adolescent market has become essential for advertisers and producers. There are numerous reasons which make the adolescent market a significant section. Youths are more engaged with shopping choices than old ages and often strongly affect family buying choices. This is all because the young age is more affected by staring at the T.V. plugs, and their discernment and assessment of T.V.C.s have prompted the end that T.V. ads are changing the view of contemplations, shopping conduct, and way of life patterns of youth.

Third hypothesis examines the link between influencer marketing and panic behavior disorder and its significant relationship. A few specialists think fits of anxiety are like "misleading problems" where our body's run-of-the-mill endurance senses are dynamic either repeatedly, too emphatically, or a mix of the two. Scientists are concentrating on how the cerebrum and body communicate in individuals with alarm confusion to make more specific medicines. Furthermore, the discoveries of this study approve that apparent gamble is liable for alarm purchasing. The outcomes show that different reasoning styles unexpectedly influence apparent gambling. Situational vagueness influences apparent gamble and frenzy purchasing, while data over-burden directs the connection between situational uncertainty and frenzy. Fourth hypothesis examines the impact of peer pressure on panic behavior disorder, and this examination process shows positive results and significant values. A companion can be depicted as a singular mature enough or one regularly interfaces with and who will likely influence one's approach to acting. Peer pressure is the close effect buddies, partners, and developing mates have on one another (Gualano, Lo Moro, Voglino, Bert, & Siliquini, 2020). It is shown by being loaded with a feeling of the pull of individual people from a companion pack towards changing following the principles of the get-together, expressing that friend pressure suggests the power applied by people of tantamount age segment or social level on one another. Peer pressure has been blamed for risky approaches to acting ordinary among youngsters, for instance, resistance, unlawful medication use, and sexual bet approach to acting. Of course, peer strain could provoke an extension in valuable ways of acting and mindsets when youngsters are influenced to swallow ways of behaving mundanely, like developing a culture of tirelessness and thought for others.

The fifth and last hypothesis is associated with panic behavior disorder and compulsive buying behavior. This variable, panic behavior disorder, is the most important Mediator. The last hypothesis has favorable significant values. Routine purchasing has been portrayed as an overwhelming longing to buy, a dependence on shopping. Rivalrous circumstances can provoke a lack of balance and withdrawal problems, from uneasiness to psychosomatic crippling. C.B.B. is a preposterous impulsive buying, while others express that it is a steady and persevering disillusionment in self-rule and, in this way, impressively more serious than inspiration purchasing (Billore & Anisimova, 2021). Through the lens of Stimulus-Organism-Response (S-O-R) the framework simplifies that influencer marketing (stimulus factor) arouse panic behavior disorder (Organism), which lead the customer to response behavior in the form of compulsive buying behavior. From the theoretical perspectives of Social Comparison theory (SCT), peer pressure effect panic behavior disorder of the customer which will result in compulsive buying behavior. Hence, through the lens Stimulus-Organism-Response (S-O-R), and Social Comparison theory (SCT) the result confirming that influencer marketing and peer pressure have an impact on panic behavior disorder of the customer and the outcome come of the customer are in the form of compulsive buying behavior (Attiq, 2015).

7. Conclusion

This study opens new doors to understanding consumer behavior and its related determinants to satisfy customer needs and desires. The major focus of this study is on compulsive buying behavior based on the cosmetic industry of Pakistan. Compulsive buying behavior changes due to panic behavior disorder of the customer in different situations, but influencer marketing can directly affect compulsive buying behavior. According to the present study, compelling buying behavior can be affected by influencer marketing in the presence of panic behavior disorder. Panic behavior has importance as a strong pillar to influence compulsive buying behavior. Peer pressure can increase and decrease panic behavior disorder in various conditions, which can cause compulsive buying behavior. This research indicates compulsive buying behavior drives two combined effects: influence marketing and panic behavior disorder and peer pressure and panic behavior disorder.

7.1. Practical Implications

The current study reflects that compulsive buying behavior depends on three factors: influencer marketing, panic behavior disorder, and peer pressure. Compulsive buying behavior develops in the cosmetic industry with the combined impact of influence marketing and panic behavior disorder. Only influencer marketing cannot create compulsive buying behavior. This result shows a need to focus on influencer marketing and panic behavior disorder to develop the cosmetic industry. On the other hand, compulsive buying behavior can be developed in another way in the cosmetic industry with the combined impact of peer pressure and panic behavior disorder. Only peer pressure cannot create compulsive buying behavior. This result shows that there is a need to focus on both influencer marketing and panic behavior disorder to develop the cosmetic industry. The cosmetic industry needs to take serious steps to strengthen influencer marketing and target panic behavior disorder. In this condition, purchasing patterns are changing from the normal routine. Every industry needs to fulfill the requirements relating to compulsive buying behavior. So, carefully monitor peer pressure and panic behavior to address the compulsive e-buying behavior.

7.2. Organizational Implications

The study holds significant implications for business and organizations operating in the cosmetic industry. The results would be significant to devise strategies that pay close attention towards influencer marketing. They need to properly arrange the vetting process and ongoing monitoring of influencer marketing in order to maintain positive brand image and consumer trust. Moreover, the organization should efficiently recognize the power of social influence which includes implementation of education that could help them towards informed purchasing decisions. Moreover, organizations should develop targeted interventions which include implementation of stress-reducing measures during the purchasing process. Hence, it would address brand loyalty and customer satisfaction as well.

7.3. Managerial Implications

The study would provide valuable managerial implications for businesses operating in the cosmetic industry. Firstly, organizations should carefully select and collaborate with influencers who align with their brand values and promote responsible consumption. This includes ongoing monitoring to ensure that influencers are not inadvertently encouraging panic behavior disorder or fostering compulsive buying tendencies. By maintaining a strategic and ethical approach to influencer marketing, organizations can protect their brand reputation and foster a positive consumer perception. Moreover, organizations should invest in consumer education and empowerment to help individuals resist peer pressure and make informed purchasing decisions. By empowering consumers with the knowledge and tools to resist peer pressure, organizations can reduce the likelihood of panic behavior disorder and compulsive buying behavior. They should focus on transparent pricing information, clear return policies, and accessible customer support services. These measures can help alleviate anxiety and panic behavior disorder, ensuring a more positive consumer experience and fostering long-term customer loyalty.

7.4. Limitations and Future Directions

Data were collected only from female students and ignored by the male respondents. Consider just the city of Lahore for this study. Just consider the single cosmetic industry; many other industries produce different products which link with the country's growth. Many other variables can be used as independent variables in this. Consider just two independent variables. This study is cross-sectional for a limited period. Examine

a single mediator of panic behavior disorder. Examine a single dependent compulsive buying behavior. This research opens the doors for the next coming researcher, and they can examine the other Mediator quality and peer pressure. Furthermore, Consider other female respondents like a housewife and professional women. In future research, collect samples from other cities in Pakistan. Based on the cosmetic industry in the coming days, this study focuses on textiles, cement, and sugar and pharmaceuticals. A longitudinal study was applied to this study shortly. Examine peer pressure as a mediator. Measure panic behavior disorder as an independent variable through mediator peer pressure on compulsive buying behavior.

References

- Adeoye, H., Ipinoyemi, T., & Ositoye, A. O. (2021). Contributions of Self-Esteem and Peer Pressure to Antisocial Behaviour among Undergraduates, Gender as Moderator. *Mizoram University Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 7(2), 227–235.
- Arafat, S. M., Kar, S. K., Menon, V., Alradie-Mohamed, A., Mukherjee, S., Kaliamoorthy, C., & Kabir, R. (2020). Responsible factors of panic buying: an observation from online media reports. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 747.
- Arafat, S. Y., Hussain, F., Kar, S. K., Menon, V., & Yuen, K. F. (2020). How far has panic buying been studied?. *World Journal of Meta-Analysis*, 8(6), 447-461.
- Attiq, S. (2015). Attention to Social Comparison Information and Compulsive Buying Behavior: An SOR Analysis. *Journal of Behavioral Sciences*, 25(1), 33-57.
- Baheer, R., Khan, K. I., Rafiq, Z., & Rashid, T. (2023). Impact of dark triad personality traits on turnover intention and mental health of employees through cyberbullying. *Cogent Business and Management*, 10(1).
- Billore, S., & Anisimova, T. (2021). Panic buying research: A systematic literature review and future research agenda. *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 45(4), 777-804.
- Bursztyn, L., Jensen, R., Ashraf, N., Dal Bó, E., Linden, L., Mahajan, A., Persson, T., Sacerdote, B., Aratanha, P., Miceli, A. Di, Fiorin, S., Jones, C., Korovkin, V., Miller, M., & Smith, B. (2014). Nber working paper series how does peer pressure affect educational investments? *Noam Yuchtman and numerous seminar participants for comments and suggestions How Does Peer Pressure Affect Educational Investments?*
- Campbell, C., & Farrell, J. R. (2020). More than meets the eye: The functional components underlying influencer marketing. *Business Horizons*, 63(4), 469-479.
- Chang, S. C., & Nguyen, T. A. (2018). Peer pressure and its influence on consumers in Taiwan. *African Journal of Business Management*, 12(8), 221-230.
- Corcoran, K., Crusius, J., & Mussweiler, T. (2011). Social comparison: motives, standards, and mechanisms.
- De Veirman, M., Hudders, L., & Nelson, M. R. (2019). What Is Influencer Marketing and How Does It Target Children? A Review and Direction for Future Research. In *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10, 2685).
- Fasbender, U., & Gerpott, F. H. (2022). Knowledge Transfer Between Younger and Older Employees: A Temporal Social Comparison Model. *Work, Aging and Retirement*, 8(2), 146–162.
- Ge, J., & Gretzel, U. (2018). Emoji rhetoric: a social media influencer perspective. *Journal of marketing management*, 34(15-16), 1272-1295.
- Gil, L. A., Dwivedi, A., & Johnson, L. W. (2017). Effect of popularity and peer pressure on attitudes toward luxury among teens. *Young consumers*. 18(1), 84-93.
- Gualano, M. R., Lo Moro, G., Voglino, G., Bert, F., & Siliquini, R. (2020). Effects of Covid-19 lockdown on mental health and sleep disturbances in Italy. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 17(13), 4779.
- Haenlein, M., Anadol, E., Farnsworth, T., Hugo, H., Hunichen, J., & Welte, D. (2020). Navigating the New Era of Influencer Marketing: How to be Successful on Instagram, TikTok, & Co. *California management review*, 63(1), 5-25.

- Hair, J. F., Ortinau, D. J., & Harrison, D. E. (2010). *Essentials of marketing research*.2. New York, NY: McGraw-Hil
- Hashem, T. N. (2021). Impact of Influencer Marketing–Three Rs–On Impulsive Purchase Behavior The Moderating Influence of Gender. *Journal of Positive Psychology and Wellbeing*, 5(4), 1481-1499.
- Herjanto, H., Amin, M., &Purington, E. F. (2021). Panic buying: The effect of thinking style and situational ambiguity. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 60, 102455.
- Islam, T., Wei, J., Sheikh, Z., Hameed, Z., & Azam, R. I. (2017). Determinants of compulsive buying behavior among young adults: The mediating role of materialism. *Journal of adolescence*, 61, 117-130.
- Japutra, A., & Song, Z. (2020). Mindsets, shopping motivations and compulsive buying: Insights from China. *Journal of Consumer Behavior*, 19(5), 423-437.
- Jin, S. V., Muqaddam, A., &Ryu, E. (2019).Instafamous and social media influencer marketing. *Marketing Intelligence & Planning*. 37(5), 567-579.
- Jung, J. (2017). Impact of motives on impulsivity and compulsivity in compulsive buying behavior. *Social Behavior and Personality: an international journal*, 45(5), 705-718.
- Kacen, J. J., & Lee, J. A. (2002). The influence of culture on consumer impulsive buying behavior. *Journal of consumer psychology*, 12(2), 163-176.
- Kaur, A., & Malik, G. (2020).Understanding the psychology behind panic buying: a grounded theory approach. *Global Business Review*, 0972150920973504.
- Khan, N. H., Ullah, F., Khan, T. A., Zafar, U., Khan, M. F. A., Mustaqeem, M., ...&Ji, X. Y. (2021). Personal-Care Cosmetic Practices in Pakistan: Current Perspectives and Management. *Clinical, Cosmetic and Investigational Dermatology*, 14, 9.
- Kukar-Kinney, M., Scheinbaum, A. C., &Schaeffers, T. (2016). Compulsive buying in online daily deal settings: An investigation of motivations and contextual elements. *Journal of business research*, 69(2), 691-699.
- Kumar, A., Ananda Kumar, A., & Babu, S. (2014). Factors influencing consumer buying behavior with special reference to dairy products in Pondicherry state. *International Monthly Refereed Journal of Research in Management and Technology*, 3(1), 65-73.
- Kuruppu, G. N., & De Zoysa, A. (2020). COVID-19 and panic buying: an examination of the impact of behavioral biases.
- Lins, S., & Aquino, S. (2020). Development and initial psychometric properties of a panic buying scale during COVID-19 pandemic. *Heliyon*, 6(9), e04746.
- Lou, C., & Yuan, S. (2019). Influencer marketing: how message value and credibility affect consumer trust of branded content on social media. *Journal of Interactive Advertising*, 19(1), 58-73.
- Maccarrone-Eaglen, A., & Schofield, P. (2017). Compulsive buying behavior: Re-evaluating its dimensions and screening. *Journal of Consumer Behavior*, 16(5), 463-473.
- Modi, S., &Jhulka, T. (2012). Consumer buying behavior: Changing shopping patterns. *Int. J. Bus. Manag.Eco. Res*, 3(3), 527-530.
- Moldes, V. M., Biton, C. L., Gonzaga, D. J., &Moneva, J. C. (2019). Students, peer pressure and their academic performance in school. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 9(1), 2250-3153.
- Morris, R., Turner, L., Whitaker, R., &Giammanco, C. (2019). The Impact of Peer Pressure: Extending Axelrod's Model on Cultural Polarisation. In *2019 IEEE International Conference on Cognitive Computing (I.C.C.C.)*. 114-121.
- Moschis, G. P. (2012). Consumer behavior in later life: Current knowledge, issues, and new directions for research. *Psychology & Marketing*, 29(2), 57-75.
- Moschis, G. P., &Mathur, A. (2006). Older consumer responses to marketing stimuli: the power of subjective age. *Journal of Advertising Research*, 46(3), 339-346.
- Moschis, G. P., &Ong, F. S. (2011). Religiosity and consumer behavior of older adults: A study of subcultural influences in Malaysia. *Journal of Consumer Behavior*, 10(1), 8-17.

- Müller, M. (2015). Assemblages and actor-networks: Rethinking socio-material power, politics and space. *Geography compass*, 9(1), 27-41.
- Nadanyiova, M., Gajanova, L., Majerova, J., & Lizbetinova, L. (2020, June). Influencer marketing and its impact on consumer lifestyles. In *Forum Scientiae Oeconomia*, 8(2), 109-120.
- Naeem, M. (2020). Understanding the customer psychology of impulse buying during COVID-19 pandemic: Implications for retailers. *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, 49(3), 173-193.
- Naeem, M. (2021). Do social media platforms develop consumer panic buying during the fear of Covid-19 pandemic. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 58, 102226.
- NGUYEN, N. T. (2021). The influence of celebrity endorsement on young Vietnamese consumers' purchasing intention. *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics, and Business*, 8(1), 951-960.
- Nielson, W. (2010). Friending the social consumer. Located at: http://blog.nielsen.com/nielsenwire/online_mobile/friending-the-social-consumer/. Accessed June, 16, 2013.
- Omar, N. A., Nazri, M. A., Ali, M. H., & Alam, S. S. (2021). The panic buying behavior of consumers during the COVID-19 pandemic: Examining the influences of uncertainty, perceptions of severity, perceptions of scarcity, and anxiety. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 62, 102600.
- Pandita, S., Mishra, H. G., & Chib, S. (2021). Psychological impact of covid-19 crises on students through the lens of Stimulus-Organism-Response (SOR) model. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 120.
- Parsad, C., Prashar, S., Vijay, T. S., & Kumar, M. (2021). Do promotion and prevention focus influence impulse buying: The role of mood regulation, shopping values, and impulse buying tendency. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 61, 102554.
- Patil, B., & Patil, N. (2020). Impact of COVID-19 pandemic on consumer behavior. *MuktShabd Journal*, 9(5), 3074-3085.
- Pradhan, R. P. (2018). Development of stock market and economic growth: the G-20 evidence. *Eurasian Economic Review*, 8(2), 161-181.
- Shamim, K., & Islam, T. (2022). Digital influencer marketing: How message credibility and media credibility affect trust and impulsive buying. *Journal of Global Scholars of Marketing Science: Bridging Asia and the World*, 32(4), 601-626.
- Sheth, J. (2020). Impact of Covid-19 on consumer behavior: Will the old habits return or die?. *Journal of business research*, 117, 280-283.
- Singh, G., Aiyub, A. S., Greig, T., Naidu, S., Sewak, A., & Sharma, S. (2021). Exploring panic buying behavior during the COVID-19 pandemic: a developing country perspective. *International Journal of Emerging Markets*.
- Singh, S. (2017). Peer pressure among adolescents in relation to family climate. *Indian Journal of Health & Wellbeing*, 8(3).
- Sivamaruthi, B. S., Chaiyasut, C., & Kesika, P. (2018). Cosmeceutical importance of fermented plant extracts: A short review. *International Journal of Applied Pharmaceutics*, 31-34.
- Suresh, A. S., & Biswas, A. (2019). A study of interrelation of psychological factors and demographic variables and its impact on compulsive buying behavior: A Marketing Perspective. *Journal of Business and Retail Management Research*, 13(3).
- Tang, T. Y., Zhang, S. K., & Peng, J. (2021). The value of marketing innovation: Market-driven versus market-driving. *Journal of Business Research*, 126, 88-98.
- Tarka, P. (2020). Influence of materialism on compulsive buying behavior: General similarities and differences related to studies on young adult consumers in Poland and U.S. *Journal of International Consumer Marketing*, 32(3), 243-267.
- Tarka, P., & Kukar-Kinney, M. (2022). Compulsive buying among young consumers in Eastern Europe: a two-study approach to scale adaptation and validation. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 39(1), 106-120.
- Tarka, P., Kukar-Kinney, M., & Harnish, R. J. (2022). Consumers' personality and compulsive buying behavior: the role of hedonistic shopping experiences and gender in mediating-moderating relationships. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 64, 102802.

- Thürmer, J.L., Bieleke, M., Wireber, F. and Gollwitzer, P.M. (2020), "If-then plans help regulate automatic peer influence on impulse buying", *European Journal of Marketing*, 54 (9), 2079-2105.
- Vinayak, S., & Arora, A. K. (2018). Social Anxiety And Peer Pressure As Predictors Of Materialism Received : 07 Jun 2018 ABSTRACT Accepted : 14 Jun 2018. *Impactjournals.Us*, 6(6), 513–524.
- Vinayak, S., & Arora, A. K. (2018). Social anxiety and peer pressure as predictors of materialism among adolescents. *International Journal of Research in Humanities, Arts and Literature*, 6(6), 513-524.
- Wang, H. H., & Na, H. A. O. (2020). Panic buying? Food hoarding during the pandemic period with city lockdown. *Journal of Integrative Agriculture*, 19(12), 2916-2925.
- Woiceshyn, J., & Daellenbach, U. (2018). Evaluating inductive vs deductive research in management studies: Implications for authors, editors, and reviewers. *Qualitative Research in Organizations and Management: An International Journal*. 13(2), 183-195.
- Yuen, K. F., Tan, L. S., Wong, Y. D., & Wang, X. (2022). Social determinants of panic buying behavior amidst COVID-19 pandemic: The role of perceived scarcity and anticipated regret. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 66, 102948.
- Zang, X., Liu, K., Qian, Y., Qu, G., Yuan, Y., Ren, L., & Liu, G. (2022). The influence of different functional areas on customers' thermal comfort—A Field study in shopping complexes of North China. *Energy and Built Environment*, 14(23), 15663.